

Journal of Social Sciences (COES&RJ-JSS)

ISSN (E): 2305-9249 ISSN (P): 2305-9494

Publisher: Centre of Excellence for Scientific & Research Journalism, COES&RJ LLC

Online Publication Date: 1st October 2020

Online Issue: Volume 9, Number 4, October 2020

<https://doi.org/10.25255/jss.2020.9.4.1509.1519>

**A Critical Discourse Analytical Study on the Significance of
Communicative Language Teaching Case study: Jordanian English
Teachers in the Southern Badia**

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study is to cast the light on Jordanian English teachers in the Southern Badia views on the importance of communicative language teaching. It is difficult for English foreign language teachers to select an appropriate method of language teaching to achieve the learning goals and the essential outcomes of the English courses that taught in different fields such as schools and colleges. CLT has indicated the track for certain procedures and strategies to accomplish essential goals for teaching English language. Teachers in teaching English as a foreign language has adopted many methods, such as Reading Method, Structural Method, Direct Method, and CLT. They seek to find the appropriate to teach English for their students and they work hard to make teaching English more effective in their classes.

Keyword:

CLT, Procedures, Strategies, Method

Citation:

Al-Awabdeh, Abdel-Hameed (2020); A Critical Discourse Analytical Study on the Significance of Communicative Language Teaching Case study: Jordanian English Teachers in the Southern Badia; Journal of Social Sciences (COES&RJ-JSS), Vol.9, No.4, pp:1509-1519; <https://doi.org/10.25255/jss.2020.9.4.1509.1519>.

INTRODUCTION

The introduction of CLT was in the second half of the 1970s. English language is one of the most important languages in the world, and this was led to the increasing the need for learning English language due to learning English provides tremendous opportunities for people all over the world. Many people have a strong desire to learn English in order to improve economic conditions or other important goals. CLT has passed in different stages over the past 50 years. It is worth noting that the beginning was in the late 1960s and extends in different stages till today. Teachers and experts seek to find the useful method to facilitate teaching and learning process.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Richards and Rodgers (2001) pointed out that CLT as approach not a method because it reflects a philosophy of teaching that is lean on communicative language use. There are several ways to defined communicative approach, such as “The communicative approach, is an approach to language teaching that emphasizes interaction as both the means and the ultimate goal of study” [2], and it defined as “The communicative approach is based on the idea that learning language successfully comes through having to communicate real meaning. When learners are involved in real communication, their natural strategies for language acquisition will be used, and this will allow them to learn to use the language.” [3]. Also it is defined as “The Communicative approach also emphasizes the ability to communicate the message in terms of its meaning, instead of concentrating exclusively on grammatical perfection or phonetics. Therefore, the understanding of the second language is evaluated in terms of how much the learners have developed their communicative abilities and competencies.” [4]

It can be said that communicative approach focus on using language and it aims to help students to use the target language in their communication, and it avoid wasting time in teaching about the language. In this approach, the useful communication is needed and the meaning is considered is paramount. Therefore, CLT is based on some principles in teaching involving certain suggestions to use method and syllabus in communication.

Basically, the syllabus is depended on;

- Developing communication skills.
- Focusing on functional development not structural development.
- Focus on fluency.
- Interaction students with students.
- The characteristics and rules of CLT
- Meaning is paramount.
- Fluency is more essential.

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- Communicative performance is not preferred purpose as communicative competence.
- The role of the learner is vital.
- Student's interaction with other students and people is encouraged.
- Communicative functions are the core.

Merits and demerits of CLT

CLT has a plethora of merits;

- Interaction between students and teacher is important and active.
- It is a try to connect learning process in the classroom and outside the classroom
- The role of the teacher is the facilitator, and the focus on learners.
- The focus of the syllabus is on the functional use of language, and it based on authentic texts. (Desai, 2015)

There are several demerits of CLT;

- It diminishes the focus on the pronunciation and grammatical errors correction since it emphasizes on the meaning and communication.
- Accuracy is neglected, and the emphasis is on fluency.
- This approach is inappropriate for beginners.

The teachers' and Learners' role in the classroom

CLT tries to give the teachers and learners new role in learning process in class. In this approach, the learners should have been an active in interaction with the teacher and other students in the class. Learners had a vital role and they should work with group and their listening should not be based on the teacher in the classroom. In CLT, learners initiate in learning and they have a responsibility in their learning. When it comes to the teachers, their role is limited in facilitation and monitoring the process of students learning, instead of following traditional way of correcting errors in writing or speaking. (Richards, 2006)

METHODOLOGY

In the current study, the searcher aims to explore teachers' views about CLT, thus survey was conducted to indicate and make short analysis about the using CLT in TEFL. Only (40) teachers took role in this survey; this study is based on teachers' responses in different schools in Jordan in the Southern Badia. The schools that participated in this survey: Al- Hashimyyah Secondary School for Boys, Al- Hashimyyah Secondary School for Girls, Al Himymah Basic for Boys, Al Himymah Basic for Girls. There are several sources of collecting information, such as interaction and observation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this section, elicited data will be analysed. The findings of the study will be presented in percentages. First, the study has found that 93% of English teachers in southern Badia of Jordan use Communicative Approach in teaching English in the classroom whereas 7% teachers use other methods and approaches in teaching English in their class as indicated in the following figure.

Figure (1)

In Figure (2), it is clear that the majority of the teachers prepared well before using this method in the classroom; 83% teachers prepared to apply this approach in their teaching before they use it but 17 % teachers did not prepare to use it.

Figure (2)

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Figure (3) shows that 73% teachers participate and do different activities by using CLT. Also, this figure indicates that 27% teachers do not use CLT in activities in the classroom.

Figure (3)

Figure (4) indicates 90% teachers satisfied with students' responses. On the other hand, 10% teachers are not satisfied with students' responses. In the classroom, are you satisfied from the students' responses for doing class activities?

Figure (4)

It is shown in Figure (5) 88% teachers think that using Communicative Approach helps in developing receptive and productive skills. Only 12% teachers think that Communicative Approach is not useful in developing receptive and productive skills.

In point of view, is Communicative Approach useful for developing listening, speaking, reading, and writing?

Figure (5)

Figure (6) clarifies that 60% teachers has been trained well before they use this approach and 40 % teachers did not expose to any kinds of training before they use it in their teaching.

Figure (6)

In the Figure (7), 83% teachers think that the textbook is designed in a good way that fit CLT goals in teaching. Only 17% teachers think the textbook does not fit to the objectives of the text book.

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Figure (7)

Figure (8) indicates that 88% teachers think their school has enough instructional materials to use in teaching by using Communicative Approach. Also, this figure shows 12% teachers do not have instructional materials in their teaching English.

Do you have enough instructional materials for using CLT in your school?

Figure (8)

Figures (9) shows that the majority of the teachers 88% think the using traditional methods in teaching English in the class needs less time. According to 12% teachers using Communicative Approach in the class does not require more

time that traditional method.

Does it take more time than traditional methods to teach English with Communication Approach?

Figure 9

In Figure (10) 90% teachers prefer teaching English by using Communicative Approach whereas 10% teachers do not prefer using Communicative Approach in their teaching.

Do you prefer teaching English in the classroom by using Communicative Approach?

Figure 10

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Figure (11) explicates 83% of teachers think that using this method reduce the power and control of the teachers on classes. while 17% think that 17% do not reduce the power relation between teachers and students.

Figure 11

1. CONCLUSION

The findings of this study reassure that CLT is essential in teaching English as foreign languages in Jordanian schools in the Southern Badia. Thus, it is used widely in teaching English and majority of the teachers prefer to use it in the classroom. The role of the teacher is totally different from traditional methods; in the Communicative Approach, teachers are only monitors and facilitators of the learning process. Also, teachers in Jordanian Sothern Badia find CLT approach more appropriate and suitable to conduct activities and they get good responses from their students. This study recommends the Ministry of Education in Jordan to train the teacher to use CLT approach before using in the classroom to be more effective in teaching English.

APPENDIX

Questionnaire for English teachers in the Southern Badia of Jordan

Number	Questions	Respond "Yes"	Respond "No"
1.	Do you use CLT in teaching English Language in the classroom?	35	5
2.	In your opinion, are you prepared to teach English by Communicative Approach?	33	7

3.	Do you participate or do activities in the classroom by Communicative Approach?	29	11
4.	In the classroom, are you satisfied from the student's responses for doing class activities?	36	4
5.	In point of view, is Communicative Approach Useful for developing listening, speaking, reading, and writing?	34	6
6.	Have you been trained before using Communicative Approach in teaching English in the class?	24	16
7.	Do you think the textbooks designed in an appropriate way in order to achieve the goals of CLT?	33	7
8.	Do you have enough instructional materials for using CLT in your school?	31	11
9.	Does it take more time than traditional methods to teach English with Communication Approach?	35	5
10.	Do you prefer teaching English in the classroom by using Communicative Approach?	36	4
11.	Do you think that CLT can help reducing the power relation between teachers and students?	33	7

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